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Hydrologic processes analysis in a high Alpine catchment: the case of the Vallon de Nant

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4 | Meteorological data

Photograph: morning view from the Glacier weather station toward the bottom (north) part of the Vallon de Nant, covered by clouds.

Before 2016, the weather station network in the Vallon de Nant was insufficient and suffered from many issues (details in Appendix 2). In this chapter, we present the design and deployment of new weather stations, addressing the many technical and environmental constraints (Sections 4.1.1 to 4.1.5) to implement the new weather station network (Section 4.1.6); some relevant meteorological data are presented in Section 4.1.7. We briefly introduce, in Section 4.1.8, the temporary high-density rainfall network composed of Pluvimate raingauges, which are presented in more detail in Chapter 5. Section 4.1.9 shows a comparison between all the precipitation measuring devices used in the catchment. Finally, the last two sections are dedicated to snowcover characterization, using lysimeters (4.2.1) and satellite images (4.2.2), two data sets which were acquired during this PhD research but could not be fully exploited within the time frame of this work

4.1 Weather stations in Vallon de Nant

4.1.1 On the challenges of a weather station network in the Vallon de Nant

The recent interest of many research groups for the Vallon de Nant (see Chapter 2) has justified the need for a reliable weather stations network. In 2016, the weather station network in the Vallon de Nant did not fulfill the new requirements and suffered many issues (see details in Appendix 4 - 1). The author of this thesis dedicated large efforts to improve the existing weather stations network according to the different need. It was particularly expected that i) precipitations would be recorded continuously throughout the year (including snowfall in winter), and additional measurements such as snowpack height, soil surface temperature, soil temperature and soil moisture, ii) the network should represent the different areas and altitudes of the catchment, and iii) a remote access to the measures and to the operating status of the weather stations was necessary to ensure the maintenance of the stations and sharing data between the different users.

We do not use any further data from the Swiss meteorological network since there are no ground measurement stations nearby, and the Vallon de Nant catchment is largely in the shadow of the Swiss weather radar network (Foehn et al., 2018b), which might see here at best rainfalls above 2800 m asl. (Marco Gabella personal communication, February 27th 2019).

4.1.2 Location and communication of the weather stations

Data transmission is a key challenge since the mobile network coverage is weak or inexistant in the most accessible parts of the Vallon de Nant. The choice was made to base the new

weather stations network on the DS3 radio dataloggers (Figure 19) proposed by Sensorscope (Sensorscope, Lausanne, Switzerland). Most of the existing sensors existing on the market can be plugged to these dataloggers (some of them requiring development from the company) and each datalogger can monitor 3 individual sensors. The dataloggers are communicating between each other by radio (868/915 MHz), creating a multi-hop network to route the data up to a master station that has the capability to send the collected data to a server via the mobile 4G LTE (long term evolution) network. The radio communication between the stations is supposed to be limited to a 1 km range, but tests in the field showed that with straight lines without obstacles between the dataloggers, distances up to 2.5 km could be reached.

Figure 19. A Sensorscope datalogger at the Glacier weather station. Each datalogger is energetically self-sufficient, with a solar panel and batteries to supply low consumption sensors up to 5 days without sun. Each box can receive 3 modules, each one connected to a sensor. An additional card can transform a datalogger into a master station and transmit the data to a server using the mobile 4G LTE network.

The new weather station network includes four locations (Figure 20, Figure 24, Table 5): 3 of them already existing (Auberge, Chalet and La Chaux), and a new one (Glacier) set up next to the terminal tongue of the Martinet Glacier at 2136 m asl. (Figure 20). The new weather station in the upper (south) part of the Vallon de Nant was expected to fulfill two main objectives: i) from a scientific point of view, the Glacier weather station ensures a better distribution of the measuring points and complete the north/south transect with the Auberge and Chalet weather stations, and ii) the Glacier weather station is also a key point for data transmission to a server as the 4G LTE network at this place is extremely good, and an

unobstructed point of view allows a radio communication with La Chaux and the Chalet weather stations (2.2 km and 2.5 km away, respectively). The curvature of the valley requires an extra datalogger to work as a hop (the relay station, see Figure 20) and link the isolated weather station of the Auberge to the rest of the dataloggers network.

Figure 20. Map showing the location of the previous 6-station and the new 4-station (Table 5) weather stations (WS) networks in the Vallon de Nant. The relay of the new weather stations network is used only as a repeater to transmit the data from the Auberge to the other stations despite the curvature of

the valley. The Glacier is the master station that transmits the data to a server through the wireless 4G LTE network.

4.1.3 Accessibility and environmental constraints

The Glacier weather station is crucial to remotely access the data from the whole network. In summer, the Glacier weather station is reached after a 6.3 km walk with 880 m of elevation gain from the Auberge weather station, without any particular risk. In winter the station is accessible by ski after 7.8 km and 1040 m of elevation gain from the village of Les Plans-sur-Bex and can be exposed to serious risks of avalanches. The access intermittency to this station for its maintenance was considered in its design in terms of energy needs and as a possible source of data gap in time series (Section 4.1.5). The Chalet, La Chaux and relay stations are also sensitive to the risk of avalanche, and to a lesser extent the Auberge weather station.

The protection status of the area (Reserve of the Muveran, see Chapter 2) imposed constraints: i) the new Glacier weather station must be at least 500 m away from the trail and be hardly visible from afar and ii) the existing Chalet weather station must be moved to a less visible place.

The Glacier weather station is located nearby the Glacier des Martinets tongue. At this place the slope is around 20° which reduces locally the risk of avalanche for the installation. To compensate for the slow movement of the terrain along the year, cable tension must be adjusted regularly. For the Chalet weather station, the new site is now located on a large rock below an alluvial cone and a couloir, not an ideal location but the only place inaccessible to cattle, visually discreet and allowing radio communications with the other dataloggers.

4.1.4 Design of the remote weather stations

Since the instruments measuring precipitations are by far the most energy-intensive devices, the energy needs of the other sensors (Table 5) will be neglected here. The most frequently used device type to measure snowfall is a heated tipping bucket raingauge, but it requires a large amount of energy to heat the raingauge when the air temperature drops below 5 °C (18W for a 200 cm² catchment surface raingauge). Furthermore, the heating induces some sublimation that biases the measures. In addition, tipping buckets are extremely error prone for snowfall measurements due to undercatch related to wind, which can potentially be prevented with fences (Yang, 2014; Nitu et al., 2018) which are however expensive and have a potentially large visual impact.

For these reasons, the choice was made to use Lufft WS400 sensors (G. Lufft Mess- und Regeltechnik GmbH, Fellbach, Switzerland) that, in addition to air temperature, air pressure and relative humidity, measure liquid and solid precipitations via a 24 GHz Doppler radar. When the air temperature is above 5 °C, the device only requires 0.17 W to run. Below 5 °C, the heating drives 20 W of energy to prevent ice formation or snow accumulation, but only when some precipitations are detected, which significantly reduces energy requirements compared to a tipping bucket rain gauge heated continuously.

Three Lufft WS400 sensors were installed at the Auberge, Chalet and Glacier weather stations. A power supply is available at the Auberge, so the energy requirements are not an issue and the Lufft WS400 is co-located with a heated tipping bucket rain gauge (Table 6).

4.1.5 Power supply

At the Chalet and Glacier locations the use of a solar panel is the easiest solution, although it remains challenging: as the valley is deep and open to the north, in winter very few hours of sun are available at these places (Figure 21), and no direct radiation reaches the Glacier for around 67 days in a row (Figure 22).

Figure 21. Trajectory of the sun along the year and shadow of the terrain at the Chalet and Glacier sites.

The maximum efficiency of a solar panel is reached with an orientation that follows the sun's course in the sky or with a fixed tilt optimizing the direct and diffuse radiations, but to limit

the amount of structure required on the field, prevent the accumulation of airborne particles (dust, snow), and have a maintenance as low as possible, the solar panel is set up fixed and vertically. The choice was made for a 330 W monocrystalline solar panel.

Figure 22. Theoretical duration of diffuse and direct radiation received daily at the Glacier weather station (46.20873° N, 7.08972° E) during the year. The diffuse radiation only account for the latitude of the point (46.2° N), while the direct radiation is also accounting for the topography based on a 2x2 m DEM (swissAlti3D, 2012b). 69 days have no direction radiation, from November 14th to January 22nd.

A pack of battery is used to store the energy produced by the solar panel during the day and compensate the sun intermittencies. However, the stored energy could never be enough to provide a continuous 20 W of power during an exceptionally long precipitation event occurring in winter. The strategy adopted is to have a pack of batteries that could be switched occasionally during winter. The choice was made for 24 V lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) batteries of 20 Ah capacity each. The LiFePO_4 technology offers a good efficiency at low temperatures and have a high energy density (5 kg per battery). On the field, one person can carry 2 of these batteries in a backpack or drag 8 of them in a pulka up to approximately 1650 m asl.

Simulations have been realized to forecast the frequency of battery switches in winter. These simulations account for i) the electricity production of the solar panels, ii) the sites accessibility (risk of avalanche after a recent snowfall) and iii) the energy requirements that depends on the duration of precipitation events. No detailed information was found at the time on the yield of a photovoltaic solar installation operating solely on diffuse radiation.

The configuration of the Vallon de Nant in winter also have advantages as i) the yield of monocrystalline solar cells (the solar cell technology having the best yield) increases with lower temperatures, ii) the snow-covered surfaces of the valley act as a reflector for direct and diffuse radiation (up to 80-90% with fresh snow), and iii) the low clarity of the sky frequently encountered during winter increases the diffuse radiation.

In absence of reference values for simple simulations, the following rules were applied to the simulations :

- The maximum power of the solar panel (330 W) improves with lower temperature (-0.004 %/°C under 20 °C).
- The solar panel produces energy only during periods without precipitations.
- During hours with direct radiation, a coefficient of 0.7 is applied to account for the fixed vertical position of the solar panel.
- A coefficient of 0.3 is applied for the diffuse radiation, with an additional coefficient of 0.5 as the diffuse radiation is used as a constant from sunrise to sunset.
- The Chalet is accessible after 2 days when a snowfall exceeds 40 cm of fresh snow or 40 mm of snow water equivalent (SWE).
- The Glacier is accessible after 4 days when a snowfall exceeds 20 mm of SWE.

For temperature and precipitation data, the 10-year records of 6 high altitude weather stations in Switzerland (belonging to the Swiss measurement network SwissMetNet, (Heimo et al., 2006)) from 2106 to 3302 m asl. under different climatic conditions (between 1165 and 2597 mm of precipitation per year) were used (Table 4). An example of simulation result is shown in Figure 23. The statistics kept for the design of the solar panel were the mean and maximum number of battery switches to do per winter, and the number of periods with lost data and its maximum duration (Table 4).

Table 4. Results of simulation based on 10-year records of temperature and precipitations data from 6 weather stations in Switzerland, and the theoretical direct and diffuse radiation conditions at the Chalet and Glacier sites. The simulations are summarized here through statistics of mean and maximum number of battery switches per year, and the number and maximum duration of data gaps.

Station name	Altitude [m asl.]	Mean annual precip. [mm]	Mean # of switches per year		Maximum # of switches per year		Mean # of data gaps per year		Data gap maximum duration [hours]	
			Chalet	Glacier	Chalet	Glacier	Chalet	Glacier	Chalet	Glacier
Pilatus	2106	1790	0.2	1.4	1	3	0	0.2	-	198
Gütsch ob Andermatt	2283	1354	1.2	2.9	3	5	0.1	0.9	14	166
Col du Grand St-Bernard	2472	2128	0.1	1.1	1	2	0	0.1	-	84
Säntis	2502	2597	0.9	2.6	3	4	0	0.4	-	189
Weissflujoch	2691	1314	1.7	2.9	4	5	0.3	1.1	9	158
Piz Corvatsch	3302	1165	0.2	1.3	1	3	0	0.2	-	25

Figure 23. Example of simulation result to evaluate the energy necessary to power a Lufft WS400 as if it was exposed to the weather conditions (temperature and precipitation amount) recorded for 10 years at the Pilatus weather station (2106 m asl.), with the theoretical direct and diffuse radiation conditions at the Glacier site. The top plot shows the periods in red when heating is required. The middle plot shows the periods in red when the station is not accessible. The bottom plot shows the energy consumption at the station, when the batteries should be switched (red dots), and periods of data loss in red when the batteries are empty and the station not accessible.

This simulation shows that the mean annual precipitation amount is not necessarily correlated with a bigger number of battery switches (2.6 switches a year with 2597 mm at Säntis; 2.9 switches a year with 1314 mm at Weissflujoch, Table 4). The reason is probably due to more intense events (at Säntis), for the same duration. The elevation (and temperatures) of the 6 stations is probably not making a big difference as a temperature below 5°C is easily reached throughout winter (Figure 23).

The conditions at the Pilatus weather station, with an elevation and mean annual precipitations close to the Vallon de Nant may not necessarily be representative, and the length of events is more critical.

However, based on these simulations, large efforts might be necessary (up to 5 switches a year) to keep the Glacier weather station working throughout winter. The probability to have data gaps remains low (from 0.1 to 1.1), but with a duration of up to 198 hours (8 days), corresponding to exceptional conditions. It was decided to go with this option anyway, despite of possible data gaps.

4.1.6 Weather stations network details

Four stations based on the Sensorscope dataloggers were set up at the Auberge, Chalet, La Chaux and Glacier sites (details in Table 5, pictures of the station in Figure 24). The stations measure every 2 minutes air temperature, air pressure, relative humidity, incoming solar radiation, wind speed and direction, surface temperature, soil temperature and water content, snow height, and precipitations (details in Table 6); exception from this list of measurements are: the Auberge does not measure direct solar radiation (technical issue), La Chaux station does not record precipitations, and the Glacier station does not record soil temperature and water content (moraine type of soil). For the 3 weather stations recording precipitation (Auberge, Chalet and Glacier), the spatial density is one station for 4.5 km², and the greatest distance between a point of the catchment and a weather station is 2.1 km.

Table 5. Location and altitude of the 4 weather stations of the Vallon de Nant.

Station name	WGS84 coordinates		CH1903 coordinates [m]		Altitude [m asl.]
	Latitude	Longitude	Easting (X)	Northing (Y)	
Auberge	46.25108° N	7.11037° E	574684	122236	1253
Chalet	46.22990° N	7.10412° E	574192	119884	1530
La Chaux	46.22795° N	7.09190° E	573248	119671	1780
Glacier	46.20873° N	7.08972° E	573071	117535	2136

Figure 24. Pictures of the weather stations at (A) the Auberge, (B) the Chalet, (C) La Chaux and (D) the Glacier. The Madd raingauge at the Auberge is located 2.5 meters above the ground, and the Lufft WS400 sensors at the Auberge, Chalet and Glacier at least 3.5 meters above the ground.

Table 6. List and properties of sensors used for the weather stations in the Vallon de Nant.

Company	Sensor	Variable	Basic characteristics	Auberge	Chalet	La Chaux	Glacier
Madd Technologies Sàrl, Yverdon-les-Bains, Switzerland	PluvioMADD	Precipitation amount (heated tipping bucket raingauge)	0.2 mm per tip	X			
G. Luft Mess- und Regeltechnik GmbH, Fellbach, Switzerland	WS400-UMB	Air temperature	± 0.2°C from -20 to 50°C	X	X		X
		Air pressure	± 0.5 hPa from 300 to 1200 hPa	X	X		X
		Relative humidity	± 2 %RH from 0 to 100 %RH	X	X		X
		Precipitation intensity (24 GHz Doppler radar)	0.01 mm/h of detection sensitivity Particle size 0.3 to 5 mm (liquid) 5.1 to ~30mm (solid) Particle velocity 0.9 to 15.5 m/s 20% Accuracy & reproducibility >90%	X	X		X
		Precipitation type	Rain/snow	X	X		X
	WS300-UMB	Air temperature	± 0.2°C from -20°C to +50°C			X	
		Air pressure	± 0.5 hPa from 300 to 1200 hPa			X	
		Relative humidity	± 2 %RH from 0 to 100 %RH			X	
Apogee Instruments, Inc., Logan, Utah, USA	SP-230	Short wave solar radiation (360 to 1120 nm)	< 1% (repeatability)		X	X	X
Young Company, Traverse City, Michigan, USA	Wind Monitor HD-Alpine	Wind speed	± 0.3 m/s from 1.0 to 100 m/s				X
		Wind direction	± 3°				X
	Wind Monitor	Wind speed	± 0.3 m/s from 1.0 to 100 m/s	X			
		Wind direction	± 3°	X			
Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, Washington, USA	DS-2 Sonic	Wind speed	± 0.3 m/s from 0 to 30 m/s		X	X	
		Wind direction	± 3°		X	X	
	STM	Volumetric water content	± 0.03 m ³ /m ³ from 0.0 to 1.0 m ³ /m ³	X	X	X	
		Soil temperature	± 1°C from -40 to +60°C	X	X	X	
Sensorscope, Lausanne, Switzerland	IRT	Surface temperature	± 2 % from -33 to +220°C	X	X	X	X
	SONAR	Snow height	± 1 cm from 0.5 to 10 m	X	X		X

The Figure 25 shows the period of data availability for each variable of each weather station. The data gaps are due to several reasons including cables cut by rodents, power supply shortage, water infiltration, data communication issues (snowpack blocking the radio signal), hardware or software dysfunction of the dataloggers, and maybe lightning stroke.

The Glacier weather station worked well during the 2016/2017 winter, without any power supply shortage. A pole of the structure broke due to an excessive tension of support cables caused by the weight of the snowpack getting packed during winter. For 2017/2018 winter, the exceptional snowfall completely buried the weather station (more than 4.5 m of snowpack was measured when the station was accessible again). Damages affected mainly the solar panel that broke due to the cold flow of the snowpack. The structure and solar panel broke again for 2018/2019 winter and the Glacier weather station was finally dismantled at the end of this data series.

Figure 25. Availability of meteorological parameters for the 4 weather stations in Vallon de Nant.

The use of the DS3 dataloggers showed mixed results as several system failures led to important gap in the data. The capacity of these devices to store data waiting for being transmitted is limited to few days (variable with the amount of data collected by the sensors) and they get definitively loss if the communication issue last too long. Furthermore, the Sensorscope company stopped its activity in 2021, so no further development or support can be done with the DS3 dataloggers.

4.1.7 Meteorological data

All meteorological data collected by the weather stations from 16 August 2016 to 14 October 2018 are publicly available on Zenodo (Michelon et al., 2021b). We give in this section some results and statistics based on the Auberge, Chalet and Glacier weather stations between 1 January and 31 December 2017 (period and stations with the least data gaps).

Air temperature and lapse rate

The daily air temperature time series from 2017 (Figure 26) are well correlated together: $R^2 = 0.95$ for Auberge/Chalet, $R^2 = 0.84$ for Auberge/Glacier and $R^2 = 0.93$ for Chalet/Glacier.

Figure 26. Daily air temperature at the Auberge, Chalet and Glacier weather stations in 2017; the mean air temperature over the year is respectively 6.1 °C, 6.3 °C and 2.8 °C (time series cumulate 16.4 %, 30.1 % and 0.8 % of data gap, respectively).

For this study, the lapse rate is an important parameter to interpolate spatially the temperature and estimate the snowmelt areas. Based on the annual mean values, we compute a lapse rate of -0.36 °C/100 m for Auberge/Glacier and -0.63 °C/100 m for Chalet/Glacier. The Chalet/Glacier lapse rate is close to the -0.65 °C/100 m standard value

from the international standard atmosphere (ISO, 1975). We explain the difference by an accumulation of cold air at the bottom of the valley in the Auberge area.

Figure 27. Altitudinal gradient of temperature along the day between Auberge and Glacier, Chalet and Glacier, for all year, February, and September. Based on common times series: between 67.6 % and 81.5 % of the period for all year, and between 97.1 % and 100 % for the individual months. The blue line is 0 °C/100 m and the red line -0.65 °C/100 m.

The Figure 27 shows that the lapse rates of Auberge/Glacier and Chalet/Glacier follow diurnal and annual cycles. Daily, the lapse rate is marked by a minimum around 1 p.m. and is weaker during nighttime. Over a year, comparing February to September, the lapse rate goes from -0.15 °C/100 m to -0.22 °C/100 m for Auberge/Glacier, and from -0.14 °C/100 m to -0.36 °C/100 m for Chalet/Glacier. The low lapse rate variation for Auberge/Glacier shows that cold air tends to accumulate in the Auberge area all the year, while the phenomenon is important

enough to be also recorded at the Chalet only during winter. The existence of cold air accumulation at the valley bottom makes the spatial interpolation of temperature over the catchment difficult. The lower the temperature gradient and the slopes, the greater the uncertainty.

Precipitations

In 2017, the Glacier weather station (2,136 m asl.) measured 1,723 mm of precipitations (rainfall and snowfall). By comparing periods with common time series, the Chalet (1,530 m asl.) recorded -2.2 % of precipitation (over 252 days), and the Auberge (1,253 m asl.) +6.5 % (over 288 days). These data tend to show a precipitation lapse rate between the Chalet and Glacier, but a higher amount of precipitation falling at the Auberge, despite its lower elevation. It could be explained either i) by a spatial variability of precipitation amounts more important than the lapse rate, or ii) by topographic effects that increase the amount of precipitations over the Auberge area.

Figure 28. Cumulated precipitations (rainfall and snowfall) measured at three weather stations in 2017. Note that the time series for this year have 17.2 %, 30.0 % and 1.2 % of missing data.

Local and high altitude winds

The wind direction measured by the weather stations in the Vallon de Nant is largely influenced by the topography of the valley (Figure 29) and each station measures predominant

wind coming from the upstream area. It reflects frequent catabatic winds, in accordance with the phenomenon of cold air accumulation during the night mentioned above.

Figure 29. Wind direction occurrence at the Auberge, Chalet and Glacier weather stations, relatively to their working periods.

Thus, the local wind measures do not give information about the general atmospheric circulation. The Figure 30 shows the occurrence of wind calculated at the 500 hPa geopotential height (approximately 5500 m asl.), in connection with precipitation events over the catchment. We see that air masses are mainly originating a sector from south-west to north, and air masses accompanied by precipitations are originating a sector from south-west to north-west. The higher probability to have precipitation events travelling from west to east highlight the higher importance, to capture most of the spatial heterogeneity of precipitation events in this area, to measure precipitations along a north-south transect than along a west-east transect.

Figure 30. Frequency of wind direction above the Vallon de Nant at 500 hPa (ECMWF ERA5) on a 6-hour time scale. The grey histogram represents the wind occurrence during the working period of the precipitation sensors, and the blue histogram the wind when some precipitations were recorded.

Solar radiation

The topography of the Vallon de Nant, characterized by a valley facing north and surrounded by high peaks shading large areas (see Chapter 2), is confirmed by the measures of solar radiations at the weather stations (Table 7) with i) low amounts during winter, ii) high amounts in summer, and iii) a large difference between the mean values.

Table 7. Statistics of daily net radiations (in W/m²) at the Chalet, La Chaux and Glacier weather stations. The mean value is computed over 217 days between 1 January 2017 and 31 December 2017.

Station	Minimum (24 Dec. 2017)	Maximum (8 Jun. 2017)	Mean (over 217 days)
Chalet	7.6	302.5	91.7
La Chaux	33.6	333.0	144.1
Glacier	6.7	322.0	90.0

4.1.8 Pluvimates raingauges

A network of 12 Pluvimate drop-counting rain gauges (www.driptych.com) was distributed across the Vallon de Nant catchment from 30th June to 4th October 2017 and from July 1st to September 23rd, 2018 to monitor rainfall (see Figure 40 in Chapter 5). Data for the 2018 season are available on Zenodo (Michelon et al., 2020). A similar deployment during the cold season would not be possible due to snowfall at all elevations throughout the winter.

The gauges are low-cost (around 600 USD each), consisting of a tube (11 cm of diameter, 40 cm of length) mounted to an aluminum funnel (Figure 31). The collected rainwater is concentrated to a nozzle that creates a drop of water of calibrated size (0.125 mL), which then falls on the impact-sensitive surface of the sensor, 30 cm below. The datalogger counts and records the number of drops over a time set up to 2 minutes. In the field, the devices are set up vertically, attached to a wooden stick. The funnel aperture is between 0.8 and 1.2 m above the ground.

The Pluvimates were set-up to count drops over an interval of 2 minutes, with an accuracy of 0.3 mm/h. Benoit et al. (2018) experimentally evaluated the device uncertainty to 5 % for rainfall intensities under 20 mm/h. Given that some of the rainfall intensities measured in the present study exceed this value (intensities up to 140 mm/h were recorded), we extended the calibration to intensities up to 150 mm/h, and few saturation effects were noticed (Appendix 4 - 2).

To prevent clogging, steel sponges were disposed in the funnel of each Pluvimate. This appeared to have caused i) a dampening effect on low rainfall intensities as it delayed slightly the beginning of very small events (lower than 1 mm/h) and ii) created drops remaining after the end of an event. The data are not corrected for these effects.

Figure 31. Drop-counting rain gauge used for rainfall measures. The Pluvimate is set-up vertically between 0.8 and 1.2 meters above the ground level (a). A tip at the end of the funnel (b) creates a calibrated drop of water that falls on the sensor, (c) which counts and records the number of drops during a given amount of time.

Additional artefacts were recorded, probably generated by strong winds creating resonance. Some stations in fact recorded very strong and highly variable rainfall over several hours during periods with high wind velocity but during days without any observed rainfall in the combined MeteoSwiss radar-rain gauge data (Sideris et al., 2014). Four periods (over 4 different days) have been manually removed from the data.

4.1.9 Comparison of precipitation measures

Figure 32 compares summer rainfall events measured jointly by the Lufft WS400 sensors located Auberge, Chalet and Glacier stations (see Section 4.1.4) and a Pluvimate (see Section

4.1.8). Although the linear regression does not show a bias ($y = 0.98x$) we note some dispersion. For the maximum rainfall over 2 minutes, there is however a certain bias, with an overestimation of the Lufft sensor relatively to the Pluvimate raingauges ($y = 0.85x$), mainly due to events measured at the Auberge.

Figure 32. Comparison (left) of rainfall amounts ($r^2 = 0.73$) and (right) maximum intensity over 2 minutes ($r^2 = 0.49$) measured at the Auberge by the Lufft sensor vs. Pluvimate rain gauge, at event scale.

Compared to the Madd rain gauge (Figure 33), the Lufft WS400 overestimates the total amount of precipitation for events over 5 mm ($y = 0.82x$), and a similar overestimation trend is observed for the maximum rainfall intensity over 2 minutes ($y = 0.70x$).

Figure 33. Comparison of rainfall amounts ($r^2 = 0.95$) and maximum intensity over 2 minutes ($r^2 = 0.72$) measured at the Auberge by the Lufft WS400 sensor vs. the Madd rain gauge, at event scale. The maximum rainfall data from the Madd sensor have been aggregated from 1-minute to 2-minute time step resolution for comparison.

Further insights into the performance of the used sensors can be obtained from a comparative measurement from MeteoSwiss between a reference measurement using a raingauge OTT Pluvio² (OTT HydroMet Sàrl, Aix-en-Provence, France) located inside a double fence intercomparison reference (DFIR), and a Lufft WS600 (similar to the Lufft WS400) located nearby outside the wind shelter (Figure 34). This comparison measurement was completed in the context of the large sensor intercomparison project SPICE (Nitu et al., 2018) but the Lufft sensor was not considered in the final project report.

Over one year and a half, the measures sometimes differ but without a particular bias. We conclude from these data that the absence of wind protection (like for the setup in the Vallon de Nant) induces a larger dispersion of the measures, but not a particular bias. The bias observed for the comparison measures in the Vallon de Nant can then be attributed to wind effect over the funnels of the Madd and Pluvimate raingauges that induce an underestimation of the rainfall measures. The height of the sensors could explain that the Madd raingauge (2.5 m above the ground, Figure 24) is more impacted than the Pluvimate raingauges (0.8 to 1.2 m above to the ground, see Section 4.1.8).

Figure 34. Comparison of measurements between an OTT Pluvio² sheltered by a double fence intercomparison reference (DFIR) and a Lufft WS600 (using the same 24 GHz sensor as the Lufft WS400), recorded between 14 Dec. 2013 and 17 Jun. 2014 at the Moléson weather station, Switzerland, by MeteoSwiss (Nitu et al., 2018). Data received from Yves-Alain Roulet (MeteoSwiss), reproduced here with the permission of the original author.

4.2 Snowcover characterization

4.2.1 Lysimeters

At the beginning of 2017 winter, 6 lysimeters have been set up within the catchment. Pairs of collocated lysimeters were set up nearby the Auberge and Chalet weather stations (2.5 m one from each other), and two others were set up near the La Chaux and the Glacier weather station (location on map Figure 20). These lysimeters have been used in a previous study (Würzer et al., 2017; Brauchli et al., 2017) and consist in a 0.45 m diameter plastic funnel covered with a metal grid (Figure 35) that collects snow melt, and snow melt rate is measured by a Decagon tipping bucket raingauge ECRN-100 (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, Washington, USA) with a 0.2 mm resolution (0.025 mm resolution due to the large collector funnel). At the Auberge and Chalet sites it was also attempted to collect the melted snow, putting a collector under the lysimeters and tubes on a low slope up to plastic bags at lower altitude.

This experience failed due to different reasons (filled up bags and flood of the raingauges, contamination of water by silicon, raingauges clogged due to an important of airborne sediments trapped in the snow).

Figure 35. (A) Picture of the co-located lysimeters next to the Chalet weather station. (B) A trench allows a tube to collect independently the melted water from each raingauge output up to two bags in an insulated plastic box at lower altitude.

The Figure 36 shows the snow melt measured by the lysimeters at the 4 locations. For the Auberge and Chalet locations, lysimeters suffered from a rapid clogging due to a large amount of airborne particles, carried before the snowfall and within the snowpack. One over the two co-located lysimeters did not work properly for this reason, and the seconds worked few months only before it was estimated to be clogged.

We see that the snowpack at the Auberge and Chalet locations, at lower altitude (1253 and 1530 m asl., Table 5), were sensitive to positive temperatures (large steps on the plot), while at the Chaux and Glacier (1780 and 2136 m asl.), the snowpack started significantly to melt respectively on 7 April 2018 and 25 April 2018. At the Chaux, a maximum melt rate of 112.0 mm.d⁻¹ was recorded (Table 8).

We remark that the mean melt rate over 3 months during the cold period (0.02 and 0.30 mm.d⁻¹, Table 8) is way inferior to the standard value of 1 mm.d⁻¹ typically used in models (Schaeffli et al., 2014) to account for cold periods water supply and is not applicable for this catchment or should at least not be an evenly distributed value.

Figure 36. Snow water equivalent (SWE) measure at the lysimeters at the 4 weather stations for 2017/2018 winter. The Chaux and Glacier time series are complete (up to the complete snowpack melt), but the Auberge and Chalet time series are cut prematurely before the period when it was estimated the raingauge measuring snow melt was flood/clogged.

Table 8. Melt rate statistics at the Chaux and Glacier lysimeters for a 3-month cold period from 15 December 2017 to 15 March 2018 and during their respective melt period.

Station	Altitude [m asl.]	3-month cold period (15 Dec. to 15 Mar.)			Melt period		
		Mean soil T [°C]		Melt rate [mm.d ⁻¹]	Duration [d]	Melt rate [mm.d ⁻¹]	
		@10 cm	@20 cm			mean	max
Chaux	1780	0.9	1.2	0.30	45	19.3	112.0
Glacier	2136	0.7	0.9	0.02	67	4.8	47.0

4.2.2 Satellite images and snow-covered areas

The evolution of the snow cover area (SCA) is analyzed using satellite images from Landsat 8 (30 m resolution) and from Sentinel-2 (10 m resolution upscaled to 30 m). The images with a cloud cover < 80 % (over the whole image) are processed manually by applying a mask over areas with eventual remaining clouds.

The SCA is estimated from the normalized difference snow index (NDSI, noted here I_{NDSI}), using the green (b_G) and SWIR-1 (b_{SWIR1} , shortwave infrared between 1,57 and 1,65 μm) bands:

$$I_{NDSI} = \frac{b_G - b_{SWIR1}}{b_G + b_{SWIR1}}. \quad (11)$$

The I_{NDSI} gives for each pixel a value between -1 and 1, and a common threshold (usually around 0.2) allows to classify snow-free from snow-covered pixels. However, it has been found that a unique value cannot satisfy some of these images, due to a significant shadow area caused by the steep slopes and cliffs closing the valley in its southern part. The sunny and shadow areas are then considered separately.

The shadow has been first identified by calculating the projected shadow based on the known position of the sun at the time of the picture and a 2 x 2 DEM of the catchment (swissAlti3D, 2012b), but i) important parallax issues appeared on the cliffs and steep slopes in the southern and eastern parts of the catchment, requiring an additional processing step, ii) the DEM is not accurate enough on the edges to give accurate results on the projected shadow, and iii) this method fails to consider additional snow layers on the edges (up to few meters in winter) and shadow caused by clouds over or near the catchment areas.

For all these reasons, the shadow areas are computed from the satellite images themselves. A shadow index S_{index} using the red (b_R), green (b_G), blue (b_B), near infrared (b_{NIR}) and SWIR1 (b_{SWIR1}) bands is defined as follow:

$$S_{index} = [(1 - b_R) \times (1 - b_G) \times (1 - b_B) \times (1 - b_{NIR}) \times (1 - b_{SWIR1})]^{\frac{1}{5}}, \quad (12)$$

and gives a value between 0 and 1. A threshold is then adjusted manually to define the shadow areas. Thus, the area is first separated between sunny and shadow area using S_{index} , and the I_{NDSI} adjusted manually for each area. The total SCA over the catchment is the sum of the SCA estimated for the shadow area and the sunny area.

The whole process relies strongly on visual appreciation, and this estimation may vary from one person to the other. In total, 53 images from Landsat 8 and 36 images from Sentinel-2

have been processed over a period of 3 years from 1 January 2015 and 1 January 2018 (Figure 37). As the satellite images can detect only snow accumulated over the forest canopy but not in the undergrowth, it has been chosen to consider only the area of catchment without dense forested areas.

Figure 37. Snow covered area in Vallon de Nant between 1 January 2015 and 1 January 2018 using 53 satellite images from Landsat 8 (L8) and 36 satellite images from Sentinel-2 (S2).

To picture the distribution of the snow-covered areas, the Figure 38 shows maps of probability of presence of snow for each month of the year. These maps are however not a robust statistic as it is based on a 2-year time series of satellite images. Note that the presence of dense forested areas at low altitude bias the probability during the winter months, for the reasons mentioned above, and that the glacier area appears as a snow-covered area.

From the SCA evolution plot (Figure 37) and the maps of probability of presence of snow (Figure 38) we see that in general the fluctuations of the snowcover occur over short periods of time (to the exception of the melt season in 2015). Due to the time interval between images, the need for high resolution images is questionable. During the first snowmelt, the snow-covered area is strongly correlated with the profile of temperature, and so to the altitude.

It would have to be verified if the area covered with snow follows a similar pattern from one year to the other. This suppose that temperature and sunshine conditions are roughly similar across the catchment during snowmelt, and that the snow layer thickness is not affecting. To compensate for the lack of temporal resolution of satellite images, multiples years of images taken during snowmelt periods could be combined and associating images together when they have the snow cover extent at similar control points, check how sparse is the snow line

in the rest of the catchment. This would allow to infer a precise spatial distribution of the snowcover at a given time by using on-field devices like soil thermometers (see Chapter 5).

Figure 38. Monthly maps of probability of presence of snow for the Vallon de Nant, based on 2 years of snow cover maps between 1 March 2015 and 1 March 2017. Each map and part of the catchment is based on a different number of snow cover maps, presented in Supplementary Material.

4.3 Summary

The design and maintenance of a weather stations network that operates throughout the year in the Vallon de Nant is challenging due to the constraints of extreme weather conditions, poor network connection, power supply difficulties relative to long lasting shadow in winter, and accessibility. The solutions developed here have shown their viability, but the multiple failures of the dataloggers, as well as the undersizing of the physical structure of the glacier weather station (to resist the snowpack accumulation) led to important data gaps. The used precipitation and raingauges do not have the same accuracy as measurement devices used

e.g. by the Swiss Meteorological Office, but offer a continuous measure throughout the year for locations where a daily maintenance is not possible and the power supply limited. The lessons learned, however, will help to equip this or other study areas under similar conditions.

For the work of this thesis, the most important meteorological parameters are the precipitation and temperature time series. The temperature recordings show the recurrent presence of cold air accumulation at the valley bottom, which implies that its amplitude and fluctuations should be studied in more detail to allow a good spatial interpolation of temperature over the catchment. Based on three measurement points, the precipitation recordings over a year showed a spatial heterogeneity which cannot be explained by a simple elevation-dependent relationship. A high density raingauge observation (0.22 raingauges per square km) is presented in Chapter 5.

Despite failures, the lysimeters network provides an estimation of the snowmelt rate for the cold season and the melt season. Satellite image analysis is difficult to automatize at such high resolution and in areas with such a predominant shadow area as in the Vallon de Nant. The snow cover area can be completed with soil temperature sensors, as presented in Chapter 6.

Appendix 4 – 1: Weather stations network in the Vallon de Nant before 2016

A first network of 6 weather stations was deployed in the Vallon de Nant starting in 2007 (details in Table 9, locations on the map Figure 20) along a transversal and longitudinal transect (Coquelin, 2008). Each station measured air temperature, relative humidity, air pressure, solar radiation, wind speed and direction, and precipitations. Two types of tipping buckets raingauges were installed: i) at the Auberge, a raingauge Madd PluvioMADD (Madd Technologies Sàrl, Yverdon-les-Bains, Switzerland) heated (when air temperature < 5 °C) to measure snowfall; ii) at la Chaux, a non-heated but the raingauge from Davis (Davis Instruments Corporation, Hayward, California, USA). In addition, four Vaïsama WXT 510 sensors (Vaïsama Corporation, Helsinki, Finland) were installed at the Chalet, Les Ayers, La Pointe des Savolaires and Frête de Saille; these sensors quantify precipitations based on the analysis of the impact of hydrometeors on a convex surface. The method is adapted to rainfall events but is unsuitable (without heating) for winter conditions as the formation of ice or accumulation of snow prevents precipitation detection (Roth, 2011).

Two of the weather stations (Les Ayers and Frête de Saille) were swept away in the following years (avalanche, storm). After 2011, different breakdowns affected the remaining stations due a lack of maintenance: communication issues, electronic failures and maybe a lightning impact caused several gaps in the data (Jean-Michel Fallot personal communication, 25 August 2021).

Table 9. Details about the previous weather stations network setup in the Vallon de Nant (locations on Figure 20).

Weather station	Auberge	Chalet	La Chaux	Les Ayers	Pointe des Savolaires	Frête de Saille
Altitude [m asl.]	1253	1500	1780	1980	2250	2580
Sensor company	Madd	Vaïsama	Davis	Vaïsama	Vaïsama	Vaïsama
Method for precip. measurements	Heated tipping bucket raingauge	Impact sensor	Tipping bucket raingauge	Impact sensor	Impact sensor	Impact sensor
Start date	19/12/2007	02/01/2008	01/03/2010	19/01/2010	02/01/2008	01/02/2008
End date	01/12/2016	2015	13/06/2019	20/08/2010	11/2015	26/10/2012
End reason	Migration to Sensorscope	Migration to Sensorscope	Migration to Sensorscope	Avalanche	Dismantling	Storm

Appendix 4 – 2: Drop-counting rain gauge calibration and data correction

Technical characteristics of the Pluvimate drop-counting rain gauges are detailed in the work of Benoit et al. (2018); for this study we extended the experimental tests to intensities up to 150 mm/h. It appears that for intensities up to 20 mm/h (99.88 % of the measured 2-min intensities during the 2018 observation period) the linear relationship between drop count and rain intensity gives a good estimate (uncertainty below 5 %); beyond 20 mm/h the linear relationship underestimates the rainfall intensities, to reach 10 % of error at 60 mm/h and 15 % at 150 mm/h (Figure 39). For this study, rainfall intensities over 20 mm/h are corrected using a polynomial law based on the experimental measures.

Figure 39. Calibration curve (on top) of the Pluvimate rain gauges based on experimental measures with controlled rainfall input, and (at the bottom) the data frequency measured in situ.

